

THE PATH TO INTELLIGENT TELECOM & AUTONOMOUS NETWORKS

TelecomGPT and Beyond ..

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10.5281/zenodo.14602730

GENERATIVE AI BOOM

TRENDS IN GENAI

Multi-modal LLM

Everything-to-everything

Sustainable GenAI

In = Out

GenAI-based Coding

First AI software engineer

GENAI

Edge LLM

Portable Large Language Models – not the iPhone 15 – are the future of the smartphone

Personal AI can redefine the handheld experience and perhaps preserve privacy too

Mark Pesce

Wed 13 Sep 2023 | 07:38 UTC

LLMs as Optimizers

Large Action Models

5 LAYERS OF INTELLIGENCE

1

CONVERSATIONAL AI

2

REASONING AI

3

AUTONOMOUS AGENTS

4

INNOVATING AI

5

ORGANIZATIONAL AI

6G IN THE MAKING

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AGI: THE CONVERGENCE OF 6G AND GENAI

Two Trends Are Emerging at Once

AI Embodiment Through 6G: Shaping the Future of AGI

Lina Bariah and Mérouane Debbah

Abstract—In the ever-evolving field of technologies, the emergence of Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), often referred to as strong artificial intelligence (AI), stands as a breakthrough in the realm of machines intelligence, promising to witness a new era of capabilities and possibilities. In particular, AGI ventures into human-level cognition, and expands to thinking, reasoning, and awareness. This imminent evolution is envisioned to be manifested through the embodiment of AI machines, allowing machines to transcend their purely computational nature and interact with the world through the different senses. Accordingly, AI agents will be grounded in the physical environment, going through subjective experiences and acquiring the needed knowledge that will lead to understanding and cognition. In our article, we explore the path towards realizing the true vision of AGI through AI embodiment, where we dig into the different types of thinking required to achieve knowledge, and hence, cognition

will rather possess a physical instantiation that will allow it to interact with the surrounding environment. Embodying AI has profound implications on AGI systems, in the sense that it will not only allow the AGI agents to understand the physical world, but to engage with it and learn from such an engagement.

The aim of this article is to delve deeper into the concept of AI embodiment as a gateway to the ultimate vision of AGI, where we open avenues for exploring how sensory grounding can forge a robust link between the machines and the environment, and therefore, paves the way to machine understanding. We set the scene for the true vision of AGI, where we unfold the reason why 6G is essential to realize this vision, and how 6G will be the key to the convergence

AI

Generative Capabilities

Computing

Memory

Human-Machine
Interaction

TELECOM-SPECIFIC LLMS

Our TelecomGPT Framework

To a new era of Telecom Agents ..

UAE's TelecomGPT: The AI Breakthrough Set to Transform Telecoms

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telecomreview.com

TelecomGPT: A Framework to Build Telecom-Specific Large Language Models

Hang Zou¹, Qiyang Zhao¹, Yu Tian¹, Lina Bariah², Faouzi Bader¹, Thierry Lestable¹, and Merouane Debbah^{1,2}

EMERGENT TECH July 17, 2024 09:26 AM GST

Why UAE's TelecomGPT could be a global game-changer in not just the telecom world but even the AI space

The Global Telco AI Alliance's introduction of TelecomGPT marks a pivotal moment for the telecom industry. This advanced AI model outshines general-purpose models like GPT-4 and is key to the UAE's 6G aspirations.

ndhu V Kashyap

Middle East AI News

Abu Dhabi researchers create first-of-its-kind telecom LLM

Khalifa University's 6G Centre and TII collaborate on building TelecomGPT

CARRINGTON MALIN
JUL 16, 2024

Share

TelecomGPT

3 Models, 3 Datasets, 3 Benchmarks!

We developed the **FIRST** LLM framework for Telecom

TelecomGPT DATASET

TelecomGPT USE-CASES

Telecom Knowledge Query

Question	What does IM stand for, and why is it considered desirable for constellations in communication systems?
Context (optional)	Option 1: Intermittent Messaging; because it allows for messages to be sent intermittently. Option 2: Index Modulation; because its combinatorial structure enables higher SNR efficiency, low-complexity implementation, and compatibility with existing coding and modulation techniques. Option 3: Instant Messaging; because it allows for real-time communication Option 4: Internal Modulation; because it modulates signals within the device itself.
Answer	Index Modulation (IM) is desirable for communication system constellations due to its higher signal-to-noise ratio efficiency compared to conventional techniques, low-complexity implementation, and compatibility with existing coding and modulation techniques.
Category	RAN1

- Reduce Time To Resolve Issues
- Obtain Comprehensive/personalized info

Telecom Task Completion & Planning

Prompt	Initiate event-based charging with decentralized and centralized unit determination, centralized rating
Response	1. Request for resource usage: A request for session establishment is received in the NF (CTF). The service is configured to be authorized by the CHF to start. 2. Units Determination: the NF (CTF) determines the number of units depending on the service requested by the UE in "Decentralized Units determination" scenario. 3. Charging Data Request [Event, Units]: The NF (CTF) sends the request to the CHF for the service to be granted authorization, and to allow the number of units, if determined in item 2, to be rated and accounted.

- Reduce operational costs & service time
- Improve field technician experience & increase succeed rates of field visits

TelecomGPT USE-CASES

Telecom Code Understanding/Generation

Prompt	Analyze this script's contribution to telecom workflows, specifying its primary functionalities. <pre>def bsc(input_bits, p_t): """ Binary Symmetric Channel. Parameters ----- input_bits : 1D ndarray containing {0, 1} Input array of bits to the channel. p_t : float in [0, 1] Transition/Error probability of the channel. Returns ----- output_bits : 1D ndarray containing {0, 1} Output bits from the channel. """ output_bits = input_bits.copy() flip_locs = (random(len(output_bits)) <= p_t) output_bits[flip_locs] = 1 ^ output_bits[flip_locs] return output_bits</pre>
Response	The script defines a function <code>bsc</code> for Binary Symmetric Channel within the telecom domain. It takes <code>input_bits</code> array of bits and <code>p_t</code> transition/error probability as parameters and returns <code>output_bits</code> after applying the channel operations. The function simulates a binary symmetric channel by flipping bits based on the given probability, which is a crucial concept in telecom communication systems for modeling channel errors and noise.

- Improve developer productivity, reducing the time to create and maintain solutions
- Improve quality and consistency of code

Telecom Math Modeling

Prompt	Please fill in the missing mathematical equation represented by < MASK > placeholder in the provided sections of a telecom-relevant research paper that discuss the system model or problem formulation. System Model: We consider a discrete-time zero-mean jointly proper Gaussian flat-fading channel with the following input-output relation < MASK > with the diagonal matrices $\mathbf{H} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{h})$ and $\mathbf{X} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{x})$. Here the <code>diag(.)</code> operator generates a diagonal matrix whose diagonal elements are given by the argument vector. The vector $\mathbf{y} = [y_1, \dots, y_N]^T$ contains the channel output symbols in temporal order. Analogous, $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, \dots, x_N]^T$, $\mathbf{n} = [n_1, \dots, n_N]^T$, and $\mathbf{h} = [h_1, \dots, h_N]^T$ contain the channel input symbols, the additive noise samples and the channel fading weights. All vectors are of length N . The samples of the additive noise process are assumed to be i.i.d. zero-mean jointly proper Gaussian with variance σ_n^2 and, thus, $\mathbf{R}_n = \mathbf{E}[\mathbf{nn}^H] = \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I}_N$, with \mathbf{I}_N being the identity matrix of size $N \times N$. The channel fading process is zero-mean jointly proper Gaussian with the temporal correlation characterized by < MASK > Its variance is given by $r_h(0) = \sigma_h^2$. For mathematical reasons we assume that the autocorrelation function $r_h(l)$ is absolutely summable, i.e., < MASK >
Response	$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{h} + \mathbf{n}$ $r_h(l) = \mathbf{E}[h_{k+l} \cdot h_k^*].$ $\sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} r_h(l) < \infty.$

- Support for Standardization and Industry Compliance

TelecomGPT OUTPERFORMS GENERAL MODELS

Multiple-Choice Telecom Questions

LLaMa 3 – 8B: 88.49%
TelecomGPT (Based on LLaMa3-8B): **94%**

Mistral – 7B: 73.25%
TelecomGPT (Based on Mistral-7B): **81.5%**

Telecom-Specific Classification

LLaMa 3 – 8B: 33.35%
TelecomGPT (Based on LLaMa3-8B): **74.3%**

Mistral – 7B: 27.84%
TelecomGPT (Based on Mistral-7B): **70.83%**

Telecom Math Modeling

LLaMa 3 – 8B: 34.45%
TelecomGPT (Based on LLaMa3-8B): **50.73%**

Mistral – 7B: 29.43%
TelecomGPT (Based on Mistral-7B): **49.26%**

*Also outperforms GPT4o!
In almost all Telecom tasks
although being much smaller
in size!*

WHAT'S AFTER TelecomGPT?

BEYOND TEXT ..

Integrating Multi-modal AI

ALL-SENSE INTEGRATION

6G: THE NEXUS OF GENAI & INTERNET-OF-SENSES

GenAI

Generative AI for Immersive Communication: The Next Frontier in Internet-of-Senses Through 6G

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Abstract—Over the past two decades, the Internet-of-Things (IoT) has become a transformative concept, and as we approach 2030, a new paradigm known as the Internet of Senses (IoS) is emerging. Unlike conventional Virtual Reality (VR), IoS seeks to enhance the real world, they can positively influence actions and behaviors, such as reaction time and detection [1]. Within this context, the IoS technology will allow individuals to experience a wide

Limitation?

Latency!

The way forward?

LLM closer to edge ...

Telecom Autonomous Agents

GENERATIVE AGENTS FOR SCHEDULING

User-Centric, Adaptive Optimization

GENERATIVE TELECOM AGENTS

Thank you ..

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